

Comparative Study on Bolted Riveted and Welded Connections-A Review

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DoI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15305434>

Abstract

Structural connections are crucial to the integrity, safety, and performance of steel frameworks. This review compares the three main connection types bolted, riveted, and welded in terms of strength, behavior, failure modes, fabrication, inspection, and cost. It traces the evolution from traditional riveted joints to the widespread use of bolted and welded connections today. Drawing from experimental studies, numerical models, and code provisions, the paper analyzes their performance under static and dynamic loads. It also highlights factors influencing connection choices and outlines current challenges and future research directions, offering practical insights for engineers and designers.

Keywords: Bolted connection, Riveted connection and Welded connection

1. Introduction

Connections are the backbone of any structural system, enabling individual elements to work together as a unified whole. In steel structures, the performance of the entire system significantly depends on the behavior and reliability of its connections. Over the years, three primary types of connections riveted, bolted, and welded have played dominant roles in the evolution of steel construction.